

Assessment of Teaching Methods, Materials and Attitude to Studying Geographical Landforms among Senior Secondary School Students in Plateau State

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Abstract

The study assessed the teaching methods, materials and attitude to studying Geographical landforms among senior secondary school students in plateau state of Nigeria. Five research question were answered during the study. The cross-sectional survey research design was employed for the study. Senior secondary three (SS3) Geography teachers and students were the target population of the study; while the stratified sampling method was used to select a sample of 170 Geography teachers and 2720 Geography students that were used for the study. Two instruments were used to collect the data for the study: Geographical landforms teaching methods and material questionnaire (GLTMMQ), and Geographical landforms effective teaching, difficulty and attitude questionnaire (GLETDAQ). Three experts each from the University of Jos validated the instruments. Cronbach alpha method was used to verify the reliability of each of the instruments. These were computed at .801 and .824 for GLTMMQ and GLETDAQ respectively. The mean and Chi-square statistics were used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses respectively. Results of the study showed that teachers were effective in using instructional material, and classroom organization and management. Field trip and discussion methods were found to be commonly used by the teachers to teach Geographical landforms. Results of the study further showed that Geography teachers did not employ modern instructional material to teach Geographical landforms. More so, it was revealed that most of the Geographical landforms were difficult for students to study and they had negative attitudes towards studying them. Few recommendations were therefore made in the light of the findings.

Keywords: Geographical landforms, Instructional methods, Instructional materials, and attitude

Introduction

Land form is conceptualized as the arrangement or organization of the land. Geographic land form therefore can be defined as the configuration of a specific geographical area or of a region or the entire earth surface. Singh (2011) defined land form as the morphology and character of the land surface resulting from interaction of physical processes and crustal movements with the geology of the surface layer of the earth. The physical process involves the vertical and

horizontal movement of crustal material of the earth, resulting from forces generated from its interior due to its movement (rotation), as well as action of agents of weathering and erosion. The study of land form is referred to as Geomorphology. Land forms are classified into three hierarchical order depending on the scale and process or mode of formation. The classification by Singh (2011) is thus explicit:

- i. Land form of first order – These are land forms of the continents and

- ocean basins such as mountains, plains, and plateaus.
- ii. Land forms of second order – These are continental slopes, continental shelves and submarine ridges. Land forms of the first and second order result from tectonic and volcanic activities.
 - iii. Landform of third order – These are called topographical features such as river valleys, sand dunes, flood plains and many other small scale topographical features. These are formed as a result of the interaction between geology and agents of weathering and erosion. The small scale land forms are subdivided according to the processes from which they are produced as thus:
 - iv. Erosional and depositional landforms – These are landforms produced from the actions of rivers (hydrolic process) and wind (aeolian process) and glacial action. Depositional land forms from the action of rivers include: alluvial fans and cones, ox bow lakes, delta of different types (arcute delta, bird-foot delta, estuarine delta, cusped or tooth-shape-delta) flood plain, natural levees, alluvial islands and sandbars. The depositional landforms from the action of wind are different types (transverse dunes, longitudinal dunes, parabolic dunes and barchans, sand-dunes, loess and sand shadow of different types, pediments playas and pajada). The converse of depositional landforms from the action of rivers and wind are called erosional landforms. The erosional landforms from the action of rivers include the following: v-shape valleys, gorges and canyons, river capture, grooves, pot holes, waterfalls, plunge holes, rapids, meanders, entrenched meanders, river terraces, structural benches

and peneplains. The erosional landform from wind action on the other hand includes: deflation hallows, desert pavements, mushrooms, zeugen, yadangs, pediplains and inselbergs, demoiselles, stone-lattec. Others include driekanter, windows and bridges and desert varnish.

Glacier as a mass movement of ice carries along with it large amount of crystal and organic material known as moraines (the debris or loads carried by glaciers). There are different types of moraines derived from the part of the glacier transporting the debris. Thus, there are lateral moraines, medial moraines and ground moraines (Singh, 2011). Mass movement of ice (Glacier) also results to the development of certain types of erosional and depositional landforms. The depositional landforms of glacier include the following: u-shape valley, cirque, (semi-circular steep sided depression), hanging-valley (spectacular waterfall), Giant Stairways (series of small ciques formed one above the other on undulating slope), Aretes and comb-ridge (steep sharp-edged ridges), horn (pyramidal peak with steep sided slopes), col (passage across a ridge in glacial environment), nunatak (solitary peak surrounded by ice and cirques, crag and tail (differential erosional surface) and truncated spurs and roches. The glacial depositional landforms includes: moraines (debris carried by glacie), till plains, drumlines (small rounded hills in till plains), eskers (longitudinal ridge-like deposits under glacier), outwash plains (debris of different sizes deposited in grades by glacier on a gentle slope).

Landforms of large scale status are categorized into two: ocean basins landforms and landforms of the continental surface. Ocean basins by definition (Weaver, 1993) are large depressions on the earth's surface filled with water, excluding shallower

continental margins of the seas. Major landforms of the ocean basins consist of ocean ridges (high areas in the ocean floor along divergent plate margins), abyssal plains (relatively flat areas in the ocean floor), ocean trenches (elongated deeps in the abyssal plains), volcanic peaks (peaks in the ocean basin that do not rise above the ocean surface).

The landforms of the continental surface consist of: fold mountains (mountains formed due to compression and upliftment of continent plates along convergent plate margins), block mountains (formed due to upliftment of crustal blocks along faulted boundaries), Precambrian shields (large continental crust unaffected by mountain building since Precambrian time), continental margins (continental crust covered by ocean water) consisting of continental shelf and continental slope.

Geographical landforms constitute an integral part of the senior secondary school Geography curriculum. This aspect of Geography is included in SSI – SSIII Geography curriculum. For instance, in senior secondary one it is featured as, ‘earth’s structure, mountains, lowlands and interpretation of physical and cultural features under map reading’. In senior secondary two, it is subsumed in regional Geography of Nigeria and map reading and interpretation (representation of relief forms), while at the senior secondary three it is treated under denudation processes, weathering and mass movement. It is therefore quite clear that the study of Geographical landforms occupies a significant place in the corpus of knowledge of Geography in senior secondary schools of Nigeria. This means that proper teaching and learning of these contents are essential if Geography should play its role as a discipline in training professionals with unique knowledge and skills critical for national development.

However, the purpose of Geography education would not be achieved under

the backdrop of poor teaching and students’ low achievement in landforms and Geography in general. The objectives of Geography (Dakur, 2018) as stated in the National Curriculum Review of 2012 is the attainment of Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and critical target of National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS). These lofty objectives would not be realized in the atmosphere of students’ failure in the subject, evidenced in the Chief Examiners’ Report of WAEC and NECO for 2019, 2020 and 2021. The chief examiners of the two examining bodies were unanimous on the unsatisfactory achievement of students in SSCE examination. The identified weakness of the students include: poor understanding of map reading, interpretation and drawing, poor understanding of concept and lack of adequate facts to tackle questions properly, inability to relate solution to problems, mere listing of points, use of incorrect words and lack of power of expression. The perceived reasons for students’ weakness by the chief examiners include non-adherence to rubrics on question paper, inadequate coverage of the geography syllabus, poor teaching by incompetent and unqualified teachers, and lack of appropriate teaching aids.

Research revealed that students have poor attitude toward Geography and particularly perceived geographical landforms as difficult aspects of Geography. Lumala’s (2011) study in Jos South LGA, Plateau State concluded that senior secondary schools students displayed negative attitude toward the study of Geography. Gofor’s (2015) study in Kanke Local Government Area of Plateau State, revealed that senior secondary school students perceived some aspects of landforms as difficult concepts to study. The students particularly perceived relief of the ocean, extrusive

volcanoes, desert landforms and glacial land forms as difficult aspects of Geography. These phenomena as exposed in research findings and reports of the Chief Examiners for National Examination Council (NECO) and West African Examination Council (WAEC) serves as the motivation for the study. Students' inability to study any aspect of geography effectively would certainly result to failure and consequently lead to the development of negative attitudes towards the subject.

Attitude, according to Travers, cited in Mangar (1013), is readiness to respond in such a way that behaviour is given a certain direction. The approach which teachers adapt for instruction and the thing to learn (content of subject matter) influences the attitude of the students towards learning (Dakur, 2018). This corroborate the earlier findings of Victor (2004) who found that students' attitudes vary according to the teaching technique the instructional material and resources used by teachers, and the content of the curriculum, particularly, the introduction of numeracy (quantitative techniques). These provided the motivation for the study. Specific focus of the study was on geographical land forms. These include the first, second and third order landforms described in the preceding discussion. These were investigated in relation to teachers' effectiveness, methods, and use of instructional material, students' attitudes and difficulties experienced in the study of the landforms.

Purpose of the Study

The study assessed the teaching the teaching methods, material and attitude to studying Geographical landforms among secondary school students in Plateau State of Nigeria. This was accomplished by assessing:

1. Teachers' effectiveness in the teaching of Geographical landforms.

2. Methods employed by Geography teachers in teaching Geographical landforms.
3. Instructional material used by Geography teachers in teaching Geographical landforms.
4. The areas of difficulty in the study of Geographical landforms being experience by senior secondary school students.
5. The attitudes of senior secondary school students towards studying Geographical landforms.

Research Questions

1. To what extent are teachers effective in the teaching of Geographical landforms as perceived by students?
2. What are the methods employed by Geography teachers for the teaching of Geographical landforms?
3. What instructional materials are employed by Geography teachers in the teaching of Geographical landforms?
4. What geographical landforms are difficult for senior secondary school students to study?
5. What is the attitude of senior secondary school students towards the study of Geographical landforms?

Methodology

The cross-sectional survey research design was employed for the study. Thus, data was collected from a representative sample in January 2022, for the purpose of making inference about the population of interest. All SS3 Geography teachers and senior secondary three (SS3) Geography students in Plateau State were the target population of the study. Based on the data collected from the Plateau State Education Resource Centre in December 2021, the population of Geography teachers was 525, while that of SS3 Geography students was 8,704, consisting of 4,488 males and 4,216 females. These were distributed in 320 government and 615 private schools. A

sample of 170 geography teachers, and 2,720 SS3 Geography students was used for the study, representing 32% and 31% of the population teachers and students respectively. The stratified sampling method was to provide equal opportunity for students in government and private schools to be represented. Thus, 32% of each stratum of schools (government and private) were randomly selected using a table of random numbers. This gave rise to 99 government and 190 private schools. All the SS3 Geography teachers and students in these schools were used as the sample for the study. Thus, 170 Geography teachers and 2720 Geography students were used for the study.

Two instruments were used to collect data for the study. These include: Geographical landforms teaching methods and material questionnaire (GLTMMQ), and Geographical landforms effective teaching, difficulty and attitude questionnaire (GLETDAQ). GLTMMQ was a nine items questionnaire for geography teachers with two sections (A & B), on methods and instructional material respectively. GLETDAQ was a 45 items questionnaire for geography students with three sections (A, B & C), on effective teaching, difficulties

experienced, and attitude towards geographical land forms respectively. GLTMMQ was validated by three experts, two in geography education and one in educational measurement and evaluation from the University of Jos. While GLETDAQ was validated by three experts, one each in geography education, educational measurement and evaluation, and educational psychology, from the University of Jos. Cronbach alpha method was used to verify the reliability of the two instruments for the study, after a pilot study conducted on a sample different from the sample for the main study. The reliability coefficient for GLTMMQ and GLETDAQ were established at .801 and .824 respectively, and thus considered sufficiently reliable for the study.

The researcher and ten research assistants administered the two instruments to teachers and SS3 students directly in the sampled schools in the second and third weeks of February 2022. Thus, the instruments were administered and retrieved immediately the teachers and students finished responding to them. Mean and chi-square statistics were used to answer the research questions and test the hypotheses of the study respectively

Results

Research Question One

To what extent are teachers effective in the teaching of Geographical landforms as perceived by students?

Table 1: Teachers' Effectiveness in Teaching Geographical Landforms

Items	During lessons on landform the following happened	\bar{X}	Decision
Instructional Behaviour	1. The teacher gives challenging exercises to students.	2.31	Not Effective
	2. The teacher uses a variety of good teaching aids.	2.43	Not Effective
	3. The teacher uses clear and easy to understand words.	2.67	Not Effective
	4. The lessons are interactive (the teacher frequently asks questions and the class provides answers).	2.89	Not Effective
	5. The teacher attends to individual students when the need arises.	2.91	Not Effective
	6. Students are motivated with the use of visual, audiovisual and concrete materials.	2.78	Not Effective
	7. The teacher utilizes the chalkboard well by writing neatly and orderly.	3.76	Effective
	8. The teacher shows good knowledge of the subject.	3.63	Effective
	9. The teacher shows enthusiasm by explaining concept with vigour.	3.58	Effective
	10. The teacher uses a variety of teaching methods.	2.93	Not Effective
	11. There is supportive and warm relationship between the teacher and students.	3.93	Effective
Socio-Emotional Behaviour	12. The teacher values and respects students' ideas and opinions.	2.82	Not Effective
	13. Students feel relaxed and secured.	3.00	Effective
	14. The teacher encourages students' interaction.	3.77	Effective
	15. The teacher shows joy for the subject and teaching.	2.41	Not Effective
	16. The teacher shows concern for students' emotional and physical well-being.	2.93	Not Effective
	17. The teacher calls students by their names to answer or ask questions.	3.98	Effective
	18. The teacher does not make fun of students by using sarcasm, cynicism or teasing.	3.82	Effective
	19. Students are given a sense of confidence.	3.57	Effective
Organizational and Management Behaviour	2. The teacher is patient with students.	3.69	Effective
	21. The teacher praises students for good answers and work, and correct bad answers and work in a friendly manner.	3.88	Effective
	22. The teacher is friendly and open to students.	3.45	Effective
	23. The teacher ensures the class is orderly and rules are respected.	3.71	Effective
	24. Lessons begin and end on time.	1.89	Not Effective
	25. Materials for lessons are adequate and ready for use.	2.30	Not Effective
	26. Lessons are not disrupted.	3.10	Effective
	27. Materials for lessons are equally shared among students.	3.10	Effective
	28. Students are given sufficient activities during the lesson and no time is wasted.	2.16	Not Effective
	29. Classroom spaces are well managed to make learning enjoyable.	2.04	Not Effective

The data in table one show that for instructional behaviour, students' mean response on seven variables were less than

the criterion mean (3.00), while their mean response on three variables were more than the criterion. For socio-

emotional behaviour, the students' mean response on three variables were less than the criterion mean, while on eight variables their mean response were more than the criterion. More so, for organizational and management behaviour, the students' mean response on four variables were less than the criterion

and more on three variables. These mean that Geography teachers were effective in their demonstration of socio-emotional behaviour, while they were not in demonstrating instructional behaviour, and organizational and management behaviour.

Research Question Two

What are the methods employed by Geography teachers for the teaching of Geographical landforms?

Table 2: Methods Applied in Teaching Geographical Landforms by Teachers

Methods	Response Analysis					
	X	F	Fx	∑fx	\bar{X}	Decision
1. Lecture Method	3	0	0	442	2.60	Not Applied
2. Project Method	3	0	0	493	2.90	Not Applied
3. Field Trip	3	34	102	595	3.50	Applied
4. Discussion Method	3	34	102	595	3.50	Applied
Cumulative Mean: $\Sigma \frac{X}{4}$						

The data in table two presents summary of teachers' response on the method they used for teaching Geographical landforms. The mean scores of the teachers' response on two methods (lecture and project methods were less than the criterion mean (3.00), while their

mean response on two methods (field trip and discussion methods) were greater than the criterion mean. These mean that lecture and project methods were not employed for the teaching of Geographical landforms, while field trip and discussion were employed.

Research Question Three

What instructional materials are employed by Geography teachers in the teaching of Geographical landforms?

Table 3: Instructional Material Used for the Teaching of Geographical Landforms

Instructional Material	Response Analysis					
	X	F	Fx	∑fx	\bar{X}	Decision
5. Charts	3	34	103	476	2.80	Not Used
6. Topographic Maps	3	51	153	663	3.90	Used
7. Models	3	51	153	544	3.20	Used
8. Pictures	3	34	102	595	3.50	Used
9. Projector	3	0	0	204	1.2	Not Used
10. Textbook	3	34	102			
11. Video Tapes	3	0	0	187	1.1	Not Used
12. Motion Pictures	3	0	0	187	1.1	Not Used

The data in table three represents summary of teachers' response on the instructional material they had used for the teaching of Geographical land forms. The teachers' mean response on charts,

projectors, video tapes and motion pictures were below the criterion mean. This means the teachers were not using those materials. The mean response of teachers on topographical maps, pictures

and textbooks were above the criterion. This means that the geography teachers were using these instructional materials for the teaching of Geographical land

forms. These mean that Geography teachers were using the traditional instructional materials more than the modern ones.

Research Question Four

What geographical landforms are difficult for senior secondary school students to study?

Table 4: Landforms that were Difficult for Students to Study

Geographical Landform	Response Analysis					Decision
	X	F	Fx	©fx	\bar{X}	
30. Plains	3	136	408	4760	1.75	Not Difficult
31. Mountains	3	340	1020	4845	1.78	Not Difficult
32. Plateaus	3	595	1785	6885	2.53	Not Difficult
33. Glacial Landforms	3	884	2652	8636	3.18	Difficult
34. Desert Landforms	3	510	1530	12631	4.64	Difficult
35. Tectonic Landforms	4	765	3060	9010	3.31	Difficult
36. Volcanic Landforms	3	510	1530	9860	3.62	Difficult
37. Ocean Relief	3	680	2040			

The data in table four contains a summary of students' response on geographical landforms that are difficult for them to study. Their mean response on six geographical landforms were greater than the criterion (3.00). These included: glacial land forms ($\bar{X} = 3.18$), Desert landforms ($\bar{X} = 4.65$), tectonic landforms ($\bar{X} = 3.31$), volcanic landforms ($\bar{X} = 3.62$), and ocean relief landforms ($\bar{X} = 3.13$).

These mean that glacial, desert, tectonic, volcanic and ocean relief landforms were difficult for students to study. More so, their mean response for three landforms were less than the criterion. These included: plains ($\bar{X} = 1.75$), mountains ($\bar{X} = 1.78$), and plateaus ($\bar{X} = 2.53$). These mean that plains, mountains and plateaus were easier (not difficult) for students in the study area to study.

Research Question Five

What is the attitude of senior secondary school students towards the study of Geographical landforms?

Table 5: Analysis of Students' Attitudes towards the Study of Geographical Land Forms

Items	Response Analysis					Decision
	X	F	Fx	©fx	\bar{X}	
42	3	1258	3774	7361	2.71	Negative
43	3	187	568	4599	1.69	Negative
44	3	697	2091	8347	3.07	Positive
45	3	986	2958	5644	2.08	Negative
38	3	1207	3621	6392	2.35	Negative
39	3	1190	3570	9435	3.47	Positive
40	3	119	357	4964	1.83	Negative
41	3	816	2448	9231	3.39	Positive
42	3	460	1380	6450	2.37	Negative
43	3	986	2958	5661	2.08	
Cumulative Mean: \sum		$\frac{X}{10}$			2.50	

The data in table five shows that the mean attitude scores of students on seven items of the instrument were less than the criterion mean (3.00). These include items: 42 ($\bar{X} = 2.71$), 43 ($\bar{X} = 2.08$), 46 ($\bar{X} = 2.35$), 48 ($\bar{X} = 1.83$), 50 ($\bar{X} = 2.37$), and 51 ($\bar{X} = 2.08$). These mean that the students responded negatively on the item. On the other hand, the data shows that the mean response of the students on three items of the instrument were greater than the criterion mean (3.00). These included items 44 ($\bar{X} = 3.07$), 47 ($\bar{X} = 3.47$), and 49 ($\bar{X} = 3.39$). These mean that the students responded positively on the items. Cumulatively, it was concluded that students had negative attitude towards the study of Geographical land form. Their cumulative mean response ($\sum \frac{X}{n} = 2.50$), was less than the criterion mean (3.00).

Discussion of Finding

Results of the study indicated that Geography teachers were effective in displaying socio-emotional behaviour during their lesson delivery on Geographical landforms. On the other hand, they were ineffective in displaying instructional and classroom organizational and management behaviour. This reveals a gap in the teachers' overall effectiveness in the teaching of Geographical landforms. This has high probable negative effect on students' achievement. Unless the phenomenon is ameliorated, is capable of negating the objectives of Geography education in the study area and Nigeria at large. The ripple effects of the phenomenon, no doubt, would pose grave danger to the value of Geography education as a contributor to national growth and development. This should be of concern to stakeholders in geography education.

The study also revealed that Geography teachers used more of the

traditional instructional materials and less of modern ones. This result notwithstanding, it is common knowledge among educators that modern teaching aids are effective tools for teaching and learning. Hence, teachers should not ignore such modern instruction aids in their lesson delivery of Geographical landforms. More so, the study revealed that many geographical landforms were difficult for students to study. The difficulties students experienced in studying Geographical landforms could be overcome if teachers apply modern teaching aids in their lesson delivery, and become generally effective in different aspects of instructional their behaviour..

Conclusion

The study concludes that teachers were ineffective in their demonstration of instructional and classroom organization and management behaviour. Field trip and discussion were the predominant methods used by Geography teachers in the teaching of geographical landforms, while others were relegated. Modern instructional materials were not employed by teachers for the teaching of Geographical landforms. Most of the geographical landforms proved difficult for students to study and they had negative attitudes towards their study.

Recommendations

1. Geography teachers need to avail themselves for opportunities available locally and globally for self-development in respect of effective teaching and learning.
2. The geography teachers should be educated through seminars and workshops on factors affecting students' attitude towards learning and how to ameliorate them.
3. The teaching of difficult concepts such as geographical landforms requires ingenuity of the teacher in terms of careful use of selected

methods and instructional material. Geography teachers should work harder in this respect to remove the difficulties students experience in studying Geographical landforms. They can also achieve this by sharing ideas and reading current materials on the content and teaching of Geographical landforms.

4. The Geography teachers should explore modern instructional materials and other active methods of teaching to experiment their effects on students' attitudes and achievement in Geographical landforms.

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